

FIVE WAYS TO WORK SMARTER, TO MAKE YOUR ENTREPRENEURSHIP A GREAT SUCCESS

Some of today's biggest businesses started out as side and passion projects. For your side business to be a success, you need to work smarter and use commercially available tools to expand your business.

Some of the most recognized and successful businesses in the world today started out as side businesses with humble beginnings.

Steve Jobs worked the night shift at Atari while spending his free time during the day on a project that would eventually become Apple. Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram were side projects that quickly flourished beyond the imagination of their creators. Meanwhile, other companies such as Spanx, Yankee Candle, and Under Armor started out as passion projects that grew into major global brands.

Of course, those success stories have most of the time been the exception rather than the rule. Much of the success of any type of business is identifying a much-needed product or service, figuring out how to finance the project, and then determining how to expand the business.

Sometimes all of this must be done, of course, while still working at your main job. Sometimes it can be exhausting trying to have a day job that pays the bills while spending time and energy on an extra business that you hope will one day become your main source of income. If you can survive the double duty long enough and find success with that side business, you can ultimately become your path to entrepreneurship, be your own boss, and if you are lucky, achieve all of your goals.

I can speak of this from experience. Personally, I've had more than one side business, six actually. I've tried everything: from vending machines in my parents' restaurants, to a failed clothing company, to my current full-time activity of helping companies find the capital they need to grow.

Shortly after college, I worked for Bonobos and helped the company move from an exclusively online business model to becoming one of the first digital native brands to have a significant physical store presence. While working there, a co-worker introduced me to affiliate marketing online. We would trade anything that paid us a good commission, and that eventually led me to online lending and, more specifically, to purchase order financing.

What started as a side business allowed me to finally transition into the finance career I had always sought. Even now, seven years later, I apply the same mindset and practices to my full-time job.

My experience with a side business taught me some valuable lessons. You have to make sure you are working efficiently in your side business because of the limited time you have. The biggest key is to work smarter and use the best tools on the market to scale your business. Then let other people handle the things you can't handle, and you will be successful.

Here are my five tips to help you manage your side business.

Use social media management tools

Social media is probably the best way to communicate with your customers and prospects today. Without the proper social media management tools, you will need to spend hours each day posting, updating, and engaging. Loomly is a tool for managing various social media platforms. It allows you to sit down on a Sunday night, set up all your social media content for the week, and then just hit the play button. Automatically update Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn so you don't have to worry about waking up in the morning before work to update your side business social media channels. Remember, a big part of being successful with a side business is about working smarter and not harder.

Hire a public relations agency

It's about finding someone who can help you create content and working to find the right outlets to get talked about, so that you don't spend all week making post proposals and trying to find ways to get heard his voice. The company can help develop a strategy and then execute it. There are affordable and accessible options for young companies that do not want to spend tens of thousands of dollars on large public relations companies.

Outsource, outsource, outsource

I cannot stress this point. Seek reliable, project-based help for features you are not good at. Upwork, for example, allows you to outsource just about any job function you want to perform, from accounting to marketing, social media management, content creation, and web design. You can hire people to do that work by the hour or by project. Or, as your business grows and you need someone to help you with customer support and respond to emails during the day when you are away, you can find someone at a very reasonable cost on that platform without committing to employees. long term until you need them.

Finding the right financial partner

To be successful, you will have to find the right financial partner. Doing so will allow you to scale your business without interfering with your personal cash flow. Bootstrapping is important and finding the right lenders for your business is vital because they are the ones who can provide you with the capital to grow. That way, you can continue to lead the lifestyle you want with your main 9-5 job. If you can, find a lender to help you with purchase order financing and accounts receivable to make sure every transaction that you do, no matter how big or small, it will be taken care of. Purchase order financing is a great program for side-hustle CEOs because you're not making a huge commitment to long-term loans or something you have to worry about paying off weekly or monthly.

Use sourcing agents

If you sell a physical product, use a sourcing agent to access your network. Your network, your knowledge and, above all, your experience in the manufacture, design and import of products will be vital for the growth of your company. There are companies that can help you design products and find the right manufacturers. In some cases, they can help you find the right products for your business, find the right manufacturers, and help you manage the entire process.

Good luck in finding success with your side business.